

The associations between weight stigma concerns, self-control resources, and physical activity during the Sport4Health program

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1. Have any data been collected for this study already?

Yes, data have been collected for this study. This is a secondary analysis of an existing dataset using data obtained from the Sport4Health study, a 12-week digital-based program aimed at increasing physical activity in a sample of obese or overweight patients diagnosed with sleep apnea. The analyses will be performed primarily by Dr. Layan Fessler, who has not worked with the data or seen it prior to analyses.

2. What's the main question being asked or hypothesis being tested in this study?

Primary hypothesis 1: We will evaluate whether higher weight stigma concerns (i.e., the anticipation of becoming a target of discrimination, Major et al., 2012) are associated with lower levels of self-control resources (i.e., objective or subjective amount of energy available for the self to initiate a self-control act, Forestier et al., 2022) in a sample of 58 overweight-to-obese individuals (body mass index [BMI] ≥ 27 kg/m²) aged from 29 to 72 years (53 men, 5 women), recruited at a hospital where they were treated for sleep apnea.

Primary hypothesis 2: We will evaluate whether higher self-control resources are associated with higher levels of physical activity in the same sample.

Both hypotheses will be tested with and without controlling for potential confounders (i.e. BMI and perceived weight).

3. Describe the key dependent variable(s) specifying how they will be measured.

Perceived self-control resources were measured using the Subjective Vitality Scale (SVS, Ryan & Frederick, 1997), at four time points: at baseline (time 1), four weeks (time 2), eight weeks (time 3), and twelve weeks (time 4) later. The SVS consists of five items (e.g., "I feel alive and full of vitality") that are rated on a Likert scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 7 (strongly agree). Subjective vitality was used to measure self-control resources because previous studies have shown it to be a reliable and valid marker of this construct (Emile et al., 2015; Forestier et al.,

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2022; Forestier et al., 2018; Rojas-Sánchez et al., 2022) Sleep duration was used to reflect physiological self-control resources (Guarana et al., 2021). This variable was measured using a triaxial accelerometer (Withings Steel HR). Total sleep duration (in minutes) will be calculated using the following formula: $[start\ sleep\ time] - [end\ sleep\ time] - [wake\ up\ duration] - [duration\ to\ sleep]$.

Physical activity was measured using a triaxial accelerometer (Withings Steel HR), which participants wore on a waist-mounted belt during waking hours each day for the entire duration of the study. Participants were asked to remove the device only during activities involving water, such as showering or swimming. A count of zero steps indicates that the participant did not wear the accelerometer, and this data will be excluded from further analysis. The cut points proposed by Tudor-Locke et al. (2011) will be used to categorize activity intensity based on steps as follows: sedentary (< 5,000 steps), low active (5,000–7,500 steps), somewhat active (7,500–10,000 steps), and active (>10,000 steps) (see Wyatt et al., 2025 for a similar procedure).

4. How many and which conditions will participants be assigned to?

N/A.

All participants were exposed to the 12-week Sport4Health program and asked to wear an accelerometer and complete questionnaires at the beginning of the study and again at weeks four, eight, and 12.

5. Specify exactly which analyses you will conduct to examine the main question/hypothesis.

Primary analyses:

To test Hypothesis 1, we will employ linear mixed-effects models (LMMs) to evaluate whether within-person variability in weight stigma over time is associated with self-control resources. LMMs are particularly suited for this analysis, as they account for the hierarchical structure of the data (i.e., repeated measures nested within participants) and maintain appropriate Type I error rates (Boisgontier & Cheval, 2016).

To disentangle within-person and between-person effects, we will center weight stigma using two distinct approaches (Hoffman & Walters, 2022). First, we will use within-person centering (group-mean centering), which involves centering weight stigma scores around each participant's mean. This approach isolates how deviations from an individual's average level of weight stigma predict self-control resources, thereby capturing within-person fluctuations. Second, we will include between-person effects, where the participant-specific mean of weight stigma (grand-mean centering) is added as a separate predictor. This allows to assess how stable individual differences in weight stigma relate to self-control resources. See Emile et al. (2015) for a similar procedure.

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Self-control resources – both self-reported (perceived) and physiological – will serve as dependent variables, while weight stigma will be specified as a fixed effect. To capture individual differences in temporal trajectories, models will include random intercepts for participants and random linear slopes for time.

To explore potential non-linear relationships, we will conduct generalized additive mixed models (GAMs). GAMs extend generalized linear mixed models by enabling the estimation of smoothly varying trends through the use of smooth functions, which model the relationship between covariates and the response variable without assuming a predefined functional form (Mundo et al., 2022).

To test Hypothesis 2, we will employ LMMs to assess whether self-control resources (both self-reported and physiological) are associated with physical activity levels, operationalized as daily step counts. In these models, daily step counts will serve as the dependent variable, while self-control resources will be specified as fixed effects. To account for individual variability in temporal trajectories, models will include random intercepts for participants and random linear slopes for time. Secondary analyses will include physical activity intensities (i.e., low active, somewhat active, and active), and sedentary level as dependent variables.

To disentangle within-person and between-person effects, we will center self-control resources using two distinct approaches (Hoffman & Walters, 2022). First, we will use within-person centering (group-mean centering), which involves centering self-control resources scores around each participant's mean. This approach isolates how deviations from an individual's average level of self-control resources predict physical activity, thereby capturing within-person fluctuations. Second, we will include between-person effects, where the participant-specific mean of self-control resources (grand-mean centering) is added as a separate predictor. This allows us to assess how stable individual differences in self-control resources relate to physical activity. See Emile et al. (2015) for a similar procedure.

Outliers will be checked on each statistical model (Leys et al., 2019), using the “performance” R package (Lüdtke et al., 2021). The median absolute deviation (MAD, Leys et al., 2013) will be used to identify univariate outliers and the Mahalanobis-MCD distance (Leys et al., 2018) to identify multivariate outliers. If the residual distributions of the model with and without the outliers are similar, the outliers will be retained; otherwise, they will be removed (Leys et al., 2019).

Statistical assumptions of normality of the residuals, linearity, multicollinearity and undue influence will be checked for all models using the “performance” R package (Lüdtke et al., 2021). If a violation of normality occurs, the data will undergo a normalization process based on the distribution curves in question (e.g., \log_{10} , cube root).

The patterns of missingness will be assessed using Little's missing completely at random (MCAR) test (Little, 1988) and visual inspection. In the absence of discernible patterns, the management of missing data will be executed through the implementation of multiple imputation, a method that employs the Multivariate Imputation by Chained Equations (MICE) R package (van Buuren &

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Groothuis-Oudshoorn, 2011). Such imputation strategy shows high robustness up to 50% missing value (Junaid et al., 2025). Subsequently, imputed datasets will be generated using default methods appropriate for continuous, binomial, and multinomial variables (van Buuren & Groothuis-Oudshoorn, 2011). The number of imputed datasets (m) will be determined based on the proportion of missing data (van Buuren, 2018).

The independent variable(s) and covariates will be standardized to z-scores.

6. Any secondary analyses?

Exploratory analyses

To explore potential non-linear relationships, we will conduct generalized additive mixed models (GAMs). GAMs extend generalized linear mixed models by enabling the estimation of smoothly varying trends through the use of smooth functions, which model the relationship between covariates and the response variable without assuming a predefined functional form (Mundo et al., 2022).

All statistical analyses will be performed in R using the lme4 and lmerTest packages for LMMs (Bates et al., 2014; Kuznetsova et al., 2017). Effect size estimates for fixed effects will be reported using marginal pseudo- R^2 calculated using the MuMin package (Barton, 2018).

In exploratory multivariable LMMs (Hypotheses 1 and 2), we will include BMI and perceived weight as covariates to control for potential confounding effects. Statistical significance will be set at $p < .05$. Since univariable and multivariable tests are independent (i.e., not simultaneously testing a joint hypothesis), no alpha correction is required for these analyses (García-Pérez, 2023).

To further investigate the relationship between self-control resources and physical activity, we will adopt an idiographic approach using GAMs (Hastie & Tibshirani, 1987). Since sleep duration has been measured using the same accelerometers as physical activity, we will use this indicator as a measure of self-control resources in our idiographic approach. In idiographic designs, a minimum of 835 observations is recommended to ensure adequate power (.80) at level 1 (Gabriel et al., 2018). To ensure robust analyses, participants with fewer than 50 observations will be excluded (Keele & Kelly, 2006). GAMs are particularly well-suited for time series data with repeated measurements nested within individuals, as they can accommodate autocorrelated error terms (Shadish et al., 2014). Nonlinearity in the relationship between self-control resources and step counts will be assessed using the effective degrees of freedom (edf) of the smoothing terms, with $\text{edf} \geq 3$ indicating the presence of nonlinearity (Shadish et al., 2014). GAMs will be implemented using the mgcv package in R (Wood, 2018), and model results will be visualized using the visreg package to facilitate interpretation of the smooth functions and potential nonlinear patterns (Wood, 2018). This approach will allow us to explore individual-specific patterns and how the relationship between self-control resources and physical activity evolves over time for each participant.

7. How many observations will be collected or what will determine the sample size? No need to justify decision, but be precise about exactly how the number will be determined.

Since the data has already been collected, the sample size will be determined using a pragmatic approach based on resource constraints (Lakens, 2022). Thus, all 58 Sport4Health program participants will be included. We will assess and address the missing data pattern to ensure $N = 58$ (see point 7 above). Sensitivity power curve will be plotted for all analyses to assess the effect sizes that can be detected at various desired power levels, ranging from 33% (the lower threshold for insufficient power) to 90% (Lakens et al., 2018; Simonsohn et al., 2014). This will be computed using the `smir` R package (Bolger et al., 2012; Green & MacLeod, 2016).

8. Anything else you would like to pre-register? (e.g., data exclusions, variables collected for exploratory purposes, unusual analyses planned?)

Individuals who attended the hospital in which Sport4Health was implemented for sleep apnea treatment were initially evaluated by a physician who determined their eligibility for the study. To take part in the study participants had to be overweight or obese (body mass index (BMI) ≥ 27 kg/m² and weight < 120 kg), aged from 25 to 70 years, be diagnosed with sleep apnea, be able to practice sport (based on the cardiologist decision) and to use the personal health monitoring devices jointly to a personal smartphone, and to give their consent. Non-inclusion criteria were being unable to understand the study due to cognition or language problems, being pregnant, feeding or parturient, and having a physical activity score < 9 (calculated using the Beacke questionnaire). Once declared eligible, the physician invited them to participate in the program. Participation in the program was made on a voluntary basis.

58 individuals took part in the study. We will exclude responses with low data quality from the accelerometer. A count of zero steps indicates that the participant did not wear the accelerometer, and the data will be excluded from further analysis (Wyatt et al., 2025).

Quality of life, anthropometric / physiological parameters, and the following physical activity-related perceptions were collected during the Sport4Health study but will not be used in this secondary analysis: Perceived risks, attitude, subjective norms, task self-efficacy, intention, action planning, coping self-efficacy, habits, decision balance.

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